

Burnup Analysis of a NuScale-like Small Modular Reactor Core with a Modified Beryllium Oxide Reflector

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803434

ABSTRACT

Typical heavy reflector design in NuScale-like SMR is made of stainless steel, which has relatively high neutron absorption cross section. To mitigate the shortage on the neutronic property of the reflector design, a modified design applying BeO as reinforcing reflector and zircaloy baffle is proposed. Meanwhile, the layout of the reflector design is optimized according to the neutron leakage distribution. This study investigates the influence of the modified reflector design on core performance for the first and the equilibrium cycle by using MCNP 6.2. With the modified reflector design, the critical burnup value increases approximately 14% and 7% for the first cycle and the equilibrium cycle respectively, and the burnup value at periphery region significantly increase due to the higher albedo of reflector. In addition, the PPF of the core in 1st fuel cycle decreases from 1.633 to 1.505 after applying the modified reflector at BOC, and the power distribution is also flattened at MOC and EOC. However, the power fraction in the periphery region excessive increases at MOC and EOC, revealing a potential to further refine the loading strategy when using the modified reflector design. The results reveal the advantage of increasing fuel efficiency and optimize the power distribution for NuScale-like SMR core. Moreover, a softer neutron spectrum is observed in the periphery region, and a negative MTC is confirmed to ensure the self-regulating effect on criticality after applying the modified reflector.

Keywords: NuScale-like SMR, Reflector Design, Monte Carlo Calculation, Burnup Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

A persistent challenge for water-cooled SMRs is the high neutron leakage associated with their compact cores. Excessive neutron leakage deteriorates fuel utilization and increases the amount of radioactive waste generated [1]. The use of neutron reflectors is essential to mitigate this issue by reflecting leakage neutrons back to the active core. In NuScale-like SMR designs, a stainless steel (SS) heavy reflector is commonly employed [2, 3]. However, despite its mechanical robustness, the relatively high neutron-absorption cross section of SS negatively affects the neutron economy [4]. As illustrated in *Figure 1*, SS exhibits a significantly higher neutron-absorption cross section than other candidate materials, suggesting that replacing it could improve reflector efficiency [5]. Furthermore, the outward neutron current distribution of a NuScale-like SMR core, shown in *Figure 2*, indicates that approximately 60% of neutron leakage occurs through the corner region. This observation highlights the importance of optimizing the reflector design in the corner region to enhance the overall albedo [6].

Figure 1. Neutron absorption and scattering cross section for candidate materials. [5]

Figure 2. Outward neutron current distribution in the NuScale-like SMR core. [6]

In our previous study, a modified reflector design is proposed for NuScale-like SMR. This design employed beryllium oxide (BeO) as a reinforced reflector in the corner region and smaller amount of BeO in the flat region, while replacing the SS baffle with a zircaloy baffle to minimize neutron attenuation [6]. The original and modified reflector configuration are illustrated in Figure 3 [7]. This study focuses on evaluating the influence of this reflector design on the performance of the NuScale-like SMR core, including its effects on reactivity, discharge burnup, power distribution and neutron spectrum variation.

Figure 3. Illustration of reflector design for NuScale-like SMR core. [6, 7]

2. METHODOLOGY

In this study, the Monte Carlo transport code MCNP6.1, in conjunction with the ENDF-VII.0 cross-section library, was employed to analyze both the initial and equilibrium cores under different reflector designs. Thermal scattering law of Be in BeO is applying to account for thermal scattering effects. The CINDER90 coupled within MCNP was directly utilized to perform depletion calculations [8]. The first part of this study aimed to obtain the equilibrium state of the NuScale-like SMR core. Subsequently, the influence of 2 reflector designs on both the initial core and the equilibrium core was examined. The depletion calculations were conducted with 20,000 neutron source particles per cycle over a total of 300 cycles, with the first 50 cycles skipped to ensure statistical reliability. The standard deviation of the criticality calculation was maintained within 30 pcm. Moreover, Tier-2 fission-product tracking in MCNP was adopted and applied consistently to all depletion cases [9].

2.1 Definition of Core State

The core in first cycle is fully loaded with fresh fuel with an initial soluble boron concentration of 1235 ppm, and the corresponding fuel loading pattern is illustrated in *Figure 4*. The refueling process involves adding fresh fuel into C-FAs (C01 and C02), replacing B-FAs (B01 and B02) with C-FAs, replacing A-FAs (A01 and A02) with B-FAs, and discharging A-FAs. In addition, D01 is discharged and filled with fresh fuel in every cycle. To simplified the calculation, the function of chemical and volume control system (CVCS), which controls the soluble boron concentration according to the fuel burnup, is neglected. Instead, an initial boron concentration is set at beginning of cycle (BOC), and boric acid is depleted throughout the fuel cycle. The refueling process is conducted every 720 days, corresponding to the design cycle length of the NuScale-like SMR. The equilibrium cycle is achieved after performing six refueling processes for both the core with original reflector design and that with modified reflector design.

Figure 4. Illustration of fuel loading pattern and operation parameter of NuScale-like SMR core. [3]

2.2 Initial Core and Equilibrium Core Analysis

After obtaining the equilibrium core state, the corresponding isotopic composition is propagated as the initial condition for subsequent calculations. Depletion analyses were subsequently performed on an assembly-wise basis with a single axial zone for both the first fuel cycle (initial core) and the equilibrium cycle. To eliminate the influence of boron concentration variation, a constant soluble boron concentration was maintained throughout each cycle — 1235 ppm for the first cycle and 0 ppm for the equilibrium cycle. These boron concentrations were determined according to the boron letdown curve provided in reference [3].

In the evaluation of the moderator temperature coefficient (MTC), a set of steady-state criticality calculations were performed at discrete moderator temperatures of 520–580 K with a 10 K step (i.e., 520, 530, ..., 580 K) in accordance with the operation condition of the NuScale-like SMR [3]. The MTC was then calculated using Eq. (1) based on two adjacent temperature points [11]:

$$MTC = \frac{(k_{n+1} - k_n)}{k_{n+1}k_n} \cdot \frac{1}{(T_{n+1} - T_n)} \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of the temperature step, k represents the effective multiplication factor, and T represents the temperature.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Analysis of Burnup Characteristics

Figure 5. Variation of k_{eff} with average burnup value in 1st cycle and equilibrium cycle.

As shown in Figure 5, the k_{eff} for the core for the 1st cycle core with the original reflector design is 1.1425, whereas it increases to 1.1493 after applying the modified reflector design. The difference of k_{eff} between the two cases gradually increases with burnup, indicating an improved neutron economy under the modified reflector configuration. The critical average burnup in the 1st fuel cycle are 16.72 and 18.42 GWd/tHM for original and modified reflector designs, respectively, corresponding to an approximate 10% increase in fuel efficiency. Similarly, for the 1st cycle core, the initial k_{eff} are 1.1407 and 1.1484 for original and modified design, respectively. The equilibrium core exhibits a comparable trend to that observed in the 1st cycle. The critical average burnup in the equilibrium cycle are 17.38 and 18.57 GWd/tHM for the original and modified designs, respectively, indicating an approximately 7% improvement in fuel efficiency. Moreover, the corresponding operation times at the end of cycle (EOC) for the first fuel cycle are 997 days and 1098 days for the original and modified reflector designs, respectively. For the equilibrium cycle, the operation times are 1014 days and 1083 days, respectively.

A comparison of the albedo values between the two reflector designs is presented in Table I. The albedo of the modified reflector remains approximately 82.5%, which is about 9% higher than that of the original design, throughout the entire fuel cycle. According to the six-factor formula,

$$k_{eff} = \eta f \rho \varepsilon P_{FNL} P_{TNL} \quad (2)$$

, where η is the thermal fission factor, f is the thermal utilization factor, ε is the fast fission factor, ρ is the resonance escape probability, and P_{FNL} and P_{TNL} represent the fast neutron and thermal non-leakage probabilities, respectively [10]. The higher non-leakage probability associated with the increased albedo in the modified design enhances k_{eff} , thereby providing additional reactivity to extend the operation period. Additionally, the average burnup increment per cycle for each FA is listed in Table II, demonstrating higher burnup increment for the FAs located in the periphery region.

Table I. Albedo of the reflector. (relative error within 2%)

Core state	1 st cycle			Eq. cycle		
	BOC	MOC	EOC	BOC	MOC	EOC
Original	0.755	0.757	0.757	0.748	0.753	0.753
Modified	0.826	0.827	0.825	0.821	0.825	0.825

Table II. Average burnup increment per equilibrium cycle for FAs. (unit: GWd/tHM)

	A01	A02	B01	B02	C01	C02	D01
Original	17.96	17.64	19.73	15.55	15.41	16.60	19.36
Modified	17.13	16.48	20.07	16.77	19.05	21.38	18.24

3.2 Analysis of power distribution

The normalized power distributions of the core at BOC, middle of cycle (MOC) and EOC for the first cycle are presented in Figure 6. The power peaking factor (PPF) is calculated as the ratio of the maximum FA power fraction to the average power of the entire core. In addition, the maximum, minimum and average power fractions are listed in Table III.

 Table III. Normalized power fraction of FA in 1st cycle.

Reflector	Original			Modified		
	BOC	MOC	EOC	BOC	MOC	EOC
Min.	0.01566	0.01742	0.01964	0.01787	0.02024	0.02178
Max.	0.04414	0.03777	0.03427	0.04067	0.03442	0.03225
Ave.	0.02703	0.02703	0.02703	0.02703	0.02703	0.02703

 Figure 6. Normalized radial power distribution in 1st cycle.

The power distribution in the peripheral region increase significantly after applying the modified reflector design, effectively flattening the overall power profile in the first fuel cycle. The decrease in PPF at BOC, MOC and EOC of the 1st cycle indicates improved core performance with the modified reflector configuration. Figure 7 and Table IV present the corresponding power distribution and power fraction for the equilibrium state.

Table IV. Normalized power fraction of FA in equilibrium cycle.

Reflector	Original			Modified		
	BOC	MOC	EOC	BOC	MOC	EOC
Min.	0.02314	0.02389	0.02385	0.02385	0.02233	0.02300
Max.	0.03129	0.03043	0.03026	0.03026	0.02986	0.03294
Ave.	0.02703	0.02703	0.02703	0.02703	0.02703	0.02703

Figure 7. Normalized radial power distribution in equilibrium cycle.

In the equilibrium cycle, the FAs in the inner region, A-FAs and B-FAs, have undergone two and one irradiation cycles, exhibiting average burnup value of 23 GWd/tHM and 12 GWd/tHM, respectively. As illustrated in Figure 8, the ^{235}U content is relatively low in the refueled FAs. The reduced fissile material content in these burned FAs leads to a gradual decrease in power fraction within the inner region as the operation progresses. Consequently, for the core with original reflector design, a flattened power distribution is achieved, accompanied by a decrease in the PPF from the BOC to the EOC. Furthermore, a pronounced increase in power fraction is observed in FA-C02, primarily due to the depletion of gadolinium burnable poison, which completely depleted at approximately 500 days as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Mass of ^{235}U and gadolinium variation in single FA within equilibrium cycle.

Under the modified reflector design, the higher neutron reflection efficiency increases the power fraction in the outer region. The consumption rate of ^{235}U in C-FAs is therefore higher than that under the original design, leading to a further reduction in ^{235}U content in the burned FAs. At BOC, when the BP content remains abundant in FA-C02, the power distribution is effectively flattened. However, at MOC and EOC, differences in the inherent burnup among the FAs and the depletion of BP subsequently induce non-uniform power distributions, with a noticeably high power fraction in FA-C02. It should be noted that the fuel loading strategy, which places all fresh fuel in the peripheral region, compensates for the higher power density in the inner region. When applying the modified reflector design, this existing loading strategy results in an excessive power

fraction increase in the periphery region. This finding suggests the potential for adopting alternative fuel loading patterns or reducing the amount of fissile material in the central FA specifically optimized for the modified reflector configuration. Despite higher PPF value of equilibrium-cycle at MOC and EOC for the modified reflector, its peak PPF (1.290 at MOC) remains 2.6% below the peak value of the original reflector case (1.324 at BOC).

3.3 Analysis of Neutron Spectrum Variation

The thermal neutron flux fraction in each FA are compared in *Figure 9*. Because BeO possesses a higher moderating power than SS, a softer spectrum is observed in the peripheral region, particularly in C01, C02, and B02. This spectrum softening is consistently observed at both BOC and EOC in the first cycle and in the equilibrium cycle. Conversely, difference in the neutron spectrum is much smaller in the inner region, indicating that the modification of reflector design primarily affects the peripheral region.

Moreover, since the original design of the FA in NuScale-like SMR is under-moderated, a softer neutron spectrum might lead to a less negative moderator temperature coefficient (MTC) [11]. To address the concern of a positive MTC that could arise from excessive neutron moderation, *Figure 10* illustrates the calculated MTC for the equilibrium core. After applying the modified design, the MTC remains negative, approximately -22 to -42 pcm/K at BOC and -26 to -55 pcm/K at EOC, throughout the operational temperature range. Compared to the core with original design, a 2%~10% increase of MTC is observed. However, despite a slight increase of MTC, it remains in the margin of recommended MTC, which should be around -30.0 pcm/K for a PWR core [12]. Therefore, this result confirms the self-regulating behavior of the reactor core when the modified reflector design is applied.

Figure 9. Fraction of thermal neutron flux in different FA. (M for modified, O for original)

Figure 10. MTC for NuScale-liked SMR core with original or modified reflector design in equilibrium cycle.

4. CONCLUSION

This study investigated the influence of a modified BeO-based reflector design on the neutronic and burnup characteristics of a NuScale-like SMR core. The modified reflector strengthens neutron reflection at the corner region, responsible for approximately 60% of leakage neutron, by using BeO reflector, while a zircaloy baffle replaces stainless steel to reduce neutron attenuation. The analysis indicates that the modified reflector increases k_{eff} throughout the entire fuel cycle, extending the critical burnup by about 10% and 7% in the initial and equilibrium cycles, respectively, thereby improving overall fuel efficiency. Moreover, the higher albedo and enhanced neutron reflection of BeO contribute to an increased power fraction in the peripheral region and a reduction in the PPF. Although minor non-uniformities appear at MOC and EOC due to inherent burnup differences, the overall core performance remains superior to that of the original design. It suggests a potential for optimizing the fuel loading pattern to achieve better synergy with the modified reflector configuration. Due to the higher neutron moderation power of BeO, a softer neutron spectrum in the periphery region is observed. However, it has no significant influence on the neutron spectrum of FAs in the inner region. Furthermore, the MTC remains negative across the operational temperature range, confirming the inherent self-regulating capability of the reactor. These findings suggest that the BeO-based reflector offers a promising approach for improving fuel utilization and core performance with sufficient MTC margin in NuScale-like SMR cores.

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